

Regarding Components of Literary Methods in Uzbek Novels		Literature Keywords: system of images, composition method, method of idea, method of creative form.
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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>The paper deals with the entirety among components of evolutionary artistic methods in the Uzbek novels. And also the category of artistic method controls mutual communication of main is studied scientifically. Overall, category of artistic method controls mutual communication of main and helper. In it the system of text and work gives a psychological process form. Recreated bases of exist information form marks advent of coverage. Identically, if ratio of expression and image consider to express of artistic measure, the ideological-artistic system of association of object is known to appear in apartness of artist. In this mean, differentiating of method requires order of components. Consequently, changing the meaning program to the project of expression components is the essential condition in the level of artistic method. Historical and organically entirety expresses formed artistic communications in this article.</p>		

The artistic work is the special world, its author makes researches relentlessly in order to achieve individual method. Method is a broad concept! The system which is rounded essence of poetic text, stabilizes in the method and appears in the beautiful view. Thus, abstractedness exists in the definition of the main concept of artistic method and we can see the sum of different theoretical coverages in it. Exist condition is commented with the theoretical complexity of scientific category and its coverage, immeasurability of measurement and its conditional nature. Speciality of artistic method's term comments that it bases logically the system of association and functions means which created poetic essence. Clearly, routing conditional expression the elements of image and imagination marks extensive nature of term. In this mean, in construction which differentiates the presentation of artistic meaning, **the system of images** which consists of idea, theme, creative form, composition evolve towards to identical factors. In confessing of "**the composition method**", "**the method of idea**", "**the method of creative form**" by russian writer M.Polyakov as the poetic elements of self formed reflects appearing itself tension of term image.

But, researching of given theoretical concepts as the special problems are not successful. Because the category of artistic method considers the main concept which supplied of logical development of poetic thought. This character is seen at the works of novelists of independent years. Let's analyze the novel "The people in the hot" of Lukman Burikhan: the outlook of the author manages independently the artistic delineation type in opening facets of character in the novel. "Ashur returned the army in the middle of later autumn when we began to attend 8th class! How he left to the army previously, he returned such unusual condition.

Usually, guys who were returning the army, got on the any car at the region center, entered the home with splendours. The car driver took dowry, even, took a sheep apart from the money if he asked.

But Ashur...

E, he-he-he-ey.!

This pleasant sound was heard from high road. We were pupils, were picking cotton under the control of Ali teacher near the road" [1, p. 181-182].

The novel "The people in the hot" of L.Burikhan considers special form of ironical mentality. Deepness of interpretation which softened the lyric expression, is seen in the novel. The main hero of image's psychology consists of tension of cause and consequence. Namely, artistic essence interpretes moving from the humoristic view of the society to sharp criticism of the reality. In the image psychology which liberalized seriousness of satiric images, is linked the activity of human with satiric scenario of setting. The character and main facets of society are showed in the interpretation which is defined by the author. The independence of hero's demonstration is limited at the unnoticed consideration of the creator's positive attitude. Although, appearance form of moral aspects is given dissociative form, the subject of the story saves its spiritual indefeasible than the author. At the part which is reminded elements of report, returning the army of Ashur is described. The variability of ironical artistic position of writer (mutual harmony of sincere love and serious contempt) than understood social communications supplies the balance of interpretation. It attracts that revising of reality at the humoristic form of the creator routed not to the hero, perhaps to the setting which caused to be his current situation. Equated with the author's speech I (Samad) marks the logical development of artistic conception and clarifies the entirety of activity, period and place. At a glance, returning the army of the guy seems to have any meaning. But the actions of routed episode accelerates regularly the main plot's lines. Also, the most essential facets of social communications are seen in the leader role which is strengthened objectivity of the creator.

Genre is one of the factors which created the method. The method is aesthetic value indicators of the art. But, any art, even any direction can not create its method. The clarity and entirety of genre are not one of the factors which created the method. Contrarily, unclarity of genre's facets and bounds specific to genre, eclecticism, causes unmethod. Especially, some researchers who are among literary and linguistics, get used to speak the method which related to literary and linguistics. Usually, in this case, artistic expression means which related art's form, is called method [5, p. 43]. Usually, the element which supplies the entirety of genre, damages stability of poetic form. Obviously, the facets of main literary system appear at the genre. The complexity and uniqueness confirms private the advent of essence and inward connection of genres-methodical entirety illustrates general meaning. Directive poetic criteria's are stabilized when method which appears in mixed form, adapts to genre or artistic form creates method.

"These days Hotam has lost his quietness. As he thought that what happened with his friend, he did not understand. He thinks why suddenly, healthy Kulmakhmud gasped as someone beaded his head. Why he said that horn was growing as mad? When Hotam is lying to look the ceiling during the long nights lonely, reminds last days with Kulmakhmud in their childhood, also

his parents, but can not find any cause. He thinks relentlessly, especially, after going to the hospital in Karagayzar his heart grieves. The words of Kulmahkmud which “horn was growing” shows that may be happen any bad event [2, p. 266-267].

In the novel "The horn" of Sh. Butaev the internal essence relies alive observations. The communication between reality with historical measure which joined them, gives description about current view of society indirectly. Expression and aggregation as the essence of artistic meaning define integrated compositional entirety. Identically, emotional and significant commence route clarity and abstractedness to each other. The option of social traditions is formed the image's psychology of mind and reality at the same time. The condition which causes losing Hotam's quietness (mad desire) depends on its practical expression. When the author describes the communications of two leader heroes, she confirms that overturning enthusiasm to bent happens differently in each person. Hotam is censorious himself than Kulmahkmud, and threats from the rapid of incident. Firstly, he is deaf due to he can not understand the essence. Secondly, he frighten to being serious of consequence. The creative evolutional and its presentation is the mentioned event which broadening analyse of psychology. It supplies to join differentiation of creator with ideological-aesthetical association of substance at the method level. In this regard, weight of information and its circuition to linguistic union form artistic entirety. Consequently, attitude of image's object and creative action among elements bestow integrity at the method. The apparent disagreements which linked with horn, eliminate tranquility between Hotam with Kulmahkmud. The author describes, analyzes and assesses colourful extents the appearing condition of exist facets in the human's talent. Closely principle observes at the broadened expression in the episode.

"Our mind which is called directive, uses treasure which is in the cellar, based on limited and strict option, the creative talent or ability which is called in literature, also, in the other art is unusual human's talent who can enter this cellar. They extricate outside dissociative pieces of our experience in the cellar, can groupe with special talent, also, after extricating outside this parts from cellar, can create them whole thing" [3, p. 82]. Indeed, literary interpretation adepts the relations of mind and sense, it treats imagination “based on limited and strict option”. If creative individuality takes into account as aesthetic center which is marked methodical maner’s essence, the essence of issue is clarified. Identically, grouping, separating and classifying interpret the nature of poetic category. In fact, the mind considers construction which is showed the sense, unnoticed essence evolves to noticed trust. Changing moral criteries to aesthetic sense feeds talent of the creator. Comparative independent hero appears position of creator and collects the facets of artistic character. We can sum that at a glance the novel "Sabo and Samandar" shows these characters.

In the novel Samandar read: -"There are not wings but I fly" (J.Rumi). This wisdom was said as for him. Although Samandar suffered from the pain of bereavement, whatever there was love ahead. Why was ahead? There was love in his heart. His heart circulated love instead of blood. This love could not go him in the earth, contrarely, was flied in the sky, mud of the

miscreant and foul world was saved, his heart kept permanently at the cleanliness condition. The feet of Samandar went on the earth, his fantasy flied in the sky as his sole. But... but suddenly disappeared all of them. As in a minute as the earth cracked and all of them crashed to the underground. Because Samandar did not feel his darling, her love's heat, failed to flagrant abyss named as LONELINESS [7, p. 308].

“Sometimes, all people felt the same feelings, but very little people knew what they thought and felt feelings of another people. Overall, spiritual observation is the result of special talent as the math or musical talent. But this is not enough. 2-3 percent of minority of people who have this talent, were born with the talent which to express their talent at the artistic form [6, p. 140]. Consequently, privatization of universal essence at the emotional expression appears artistic relation. Precisely, density of relationship between generality and identity create expression need. Namely, philosophical, syntactic-compositional and grammatical-semantic power of observation change to factors which create creative apartness. Sorting of social-spiritual-educational extents which formed in artistic and vital relation, supplies privatization of talent of the creator. In this mean, tension of compositional principles and image means face serious evolings at the literary interpretation of each writer. If creative process creates the dialogic relations between author with reader's mind, main facets of artistic method joins task. In fact, objectization and subjectization of object are equal to each other at the advent.

"After yearly ceremony of deceased Urok, came officials to the our village.. Flashed in three colours: white, black, red the car “Volga” stopped near the farm’s office. Streets looked like as the bee nest. Sweeping, spraying water peaked up. Some people said that they were auditors, the others said that they were travelers. The people did not mistake! Visited people with splendor were the community which inspected stealthily, they inspected slightly, gusted and travelled.

They were five or six people. They were vaunting placidly in the beautiful cloths” [1, p. 201].

Usual daily detail defines operativness of observation which related to form of image of the novel “The people in the hot”. Visits of officials to the village is showed. Showing details of centralized state policy is formed ironical attitude to the social regime by author. The writer reveals the partners of the society which is built based on vanity, lie and fear one by one. The author assesses regretly forceful dedication, false self sacrifice, aspiring flaws in the society. It is emphasized logically to the leaders who is clamored for gaining people’s attention, trying for others look in the piece. The falsity, quip irony, sarcasm which seemed during the whole image, are upraised to the expression center. The creator reflects that “in the novel being of deceiving people “conscience” of the people and depreciating of the people such Abdulla surly” Because Abdulla does not do anything for seeing people. Every talking speech and step are based on internal logic, mental base. He lives good for knowing what he must do. For living good, undependent on others he respects himself. Respected himself and looked like everyone "all" do not like. The author shows masterfully psychology of Abdulla which comes to his brother's death

ceremony. In the novel seems that the author knows psychology of human. He imagines definitely that human upraises with which aspect, his (her) nature is showed clarity” [4, p. 317-318]. Indeed, in the novel inclination of researching psychology of human and society are visibility. According to this, human has to fight against idiotic demerits of setting and embodied exist demerits in his (her) talent. The creative logic of whole novel is linked the coverage of disagreements. Obsessing the mental criteria than benefits and needs follows the society’s decadence. Chosen impressions as special artistic proof of human's activity clarifies quality indicators of society members. The ironical-humoristic entirety of expression joins long and short interpretations. In this case, presentation and practice consider the leader complemented components. Consequently, upraising to the main role of human's benefits and needs considers the head criteria of every period.

"In the right side of the stage is sitting the dog which has three heads. It seems that its light blue eyes is controlling three side of the hall.

This dog’s three heads are circle. As good feeded, white-blue furs flash, because of length lies down on the earth as the women's dress. At dog's sitting, looking have any boredom, sadness, also kindness, regret. As trying not to forget must to guard, it does not distract various things, does not pay attention events in its around, does not frighten anybody and does not bark. Although anybody does not interested in appearing of dog in the edge of the stage, does not surprise as seen it previously, even they do not think to ask from each other why dog's head are three.

As this condition is very natural. It seems that on the stage and the audience are showing as accustoming because of seeing dogs in the crossroads” [2, p. 239].

The three head dog – Kerber episode which is given from Greeks' mythology, helps to supply deepness of analysis to Sh.Butaev. At the mythological epos the guarder animal of the exit path from underground deaths' kingdom is used as the symbol which supplies the balance. In the piece of the novel three-heads dog is showed as the strength which controls human's purpose and intensions. Mister Ximer is the impartial observer who learned perfectly whole elements of mankind. Thus, each action of hero consists of bents which is formed clarity purpose. When the author eliminates differs among period, he collects problems of mankind development: lust and the entirety of essence to one point. The measures (yesterday, today, tomorrow) defenseless in front of this trust. The writer details at the same time tragedy of mankind which drowns to swap and developing. The current situation psychology and philosophy of human confirms to be the most complexity issue of existence.

The specific characters of evolutional of artistic method is showed in the components of the novel "Sabo and Samandar" of U.Khamdam:

"-Give me a cup of ice-cold water, niece, -said Samandar as entering as from outside to daughter of Usman.

- In winter do you drink an ice-cold water, my son? - Khanifa aya who worried, turned out for him.

-Aching whole body, I do not know... - said when was taking a cup from niece hand. But he could not take a cup, the cup dropped on the iced earth and broke. -Ahh!... - said Samandar and failed.

- Have you not a temperature, my son? - said his mother and held his forehead. - You have a temperature, Samandar... - Stand up, enter to the room - Khanifa aya pulled his hands. - Stand up, my son! There is not strength at me?... Daughter! - said and looked for daughter-in-law. Kanoat, daughter, call your mother, find out Usman, the doctor needs...

When the doctor arrived Samandar was delirious from the temperature" [7, p. 328-329].

The culmination point shakes the heart of the readers in this piece which is taken the novel. The tragic tune which mixed to the whole novel, upraises to the high level in the piece. Samandar who did not want to inure beats of the life, did not know himself because of the temperature. The love concept was his lifestyle. But the love epos ended tragically. The concept which is expressed mental purpose, faces beats of social communications sharply. The new self reproduced interpretation of traditional theme, seems unnatural at a glance. Changeable of science-technology and traditional criterias causes to collapse of human's creed. In this situation, grow thing of strong mental criteria is impossible event. But artistic reality of the novel forms colourful social-household based on logically. The new appearance of understanding of the universe joins with human's essence directly and indirectly. Actually, tension which linked with cause and consequence growths from cultural criteria of society.

"The heartache which specific to each person, creates special power in the writer. It seems that it is an adjunct which needs to writer's life and it gives power to writer's life. Intention for writing in the history of any minutes of the event maybe cause incomparable achievements. Of course, this new traditions, new philosophical conceptions, remarkable scientific inventions must not the leader idea, any piece of any poem, any phrase of prose which reflect any piece of reality, maybe in the place of such tradition. Certainly, it maybe show brighter at the created works by fantasy. In such works world is described fully changed form, this world obeys fully another principles" [3, p. 248-249]. In it harmony and tension require each other. Virtually, any updated tradition does not change original essence of human. Only, difference is showed in this essence and its expression. This difference feed spiritual excitement which specific to mankind. It emphasizes that traditional criterias relates to social-philosophical mentality. Actually, compounding of specific affects mental criterias.

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meaning program to the project of expression components is the essential condition in the level of artistic method.

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